

**AGENT-BASED
SUPPORT TOOL FOR
THE DEVELOPMENT
OF AGRICULTURE POLICIES**

D9.4 - Corporate Identity

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www.agricore-project.eu

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Executive Summary

The present document is the deliverable “D9.4- AGRICORE corporate identity” of the AGRICORE project, funded from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 816078, and presents the visual identity and elements of the project developed in its first three months.

This deliverable is created in accordance with the description of the Work Package 9: Communication and Dissemination of AGRICORE and the particular tasks 9.3 - Communication activities and 9.4 - Dissemination activities as presented in the Grant Agreement. These tasks describe the main communication and dissemination activities which target maximum take-up of knowledge and exploitation of the project results. In this context, the development of an attractive and consistent corporate identity for AGRICORE will facilitate meeting, communication and dissemination targets. This includes the creation of a project logo and the colour scheme as well as relevant graphics and templates that will accompany the project during its lifetime, as a harmonised way of transmitting the project image to the public.

The purpose of this document is to provide a detailed description of the work performed in the frame of developing the corporate identity of the AGRICORE project.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full name
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
QR	Quick Response
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

Deliverable D9.4 of the AGRICORE project is part of the overall dissemination and exploitation plan of the project. Indeed, one of the main objectives of the AGRICORE is to proceed in targeted dissemination and communication activities of the results of the project. Through dissemination activities knowledge and results are transferred to selected audiences that can make the best use of it, maximizing also the impact of this research. This report describes the development of the corporate identity of AGRICORE, that will contribute to the accomplishment of these objectives, along with relevant materials that are commonly used during the implementation of a project. The purpose of the corporate identity is based on two basic pillars, particularly:

- **Communication:** the right use of the developed visual elements allows effective and consistent communication of the project concept and results, i.e. for dissemination actions. Thus, they can act as communication tools.
- **Organization:** A common design of the consortium's communication tools, including presentations and documents, will save time and effort for the members of the consortium, since no further design work will be necessary.

The overall goal of this deliverable is to maximise the impact of the AGRICORE project by creating a visual association with its concept and overall objective.

At the same time, a holistic website and social media presence are of great importance in the dissemination and communication strategy. For this purpose, the AGRICORE website was developed, and social media accounts dedicated to the project were created. The latest dissemination and communication activities will be available online from M4, providing insights to the most important actions of the consortium team. Although the created social media accounts are detailed in this deliverable, the process of creating the website is reported in the corresponding deliverable *D9.5- AGRICORE project website*, which is submitted also in M4.

2 Project corporate identity

For the AGRICORE consortium, it was a prime target to have a clearly defined, unique and consistent visual identity which will be available from the very start of the project and can be used both in printed and digital media.

The AGRICORE corporate identity is the “soul” of the project and it represents its philosophy, helping the project to be easily recognisable in-and outside the consortium, allowing a wide dissemination of its results.

The corporate identity is mainly based on the development of the logo and the background image which build the frame of any document or output of the AGRICORE project. These two elements are used in all dissemination materials, as well as in the design of the AGRICORE webpage and the social media accounts. Moreover, it is designed to ensure that throughout the 4 years of operation of the AGRICORE project the members of the project consortium can prepare and use the communication materials in a coherent way.

2.1 The AGRICORE project Logo

The first step within the communication strategy of the Agricore was to create a clearly recognisable project logo that would reflect the field of interest in a modern designed manner. Considering a holistic and multidisciplinary approach the procedure that was followed to identify the most appropriate logo was through voting.

2.1.1 Voting procedure

Even before the official Kick-off Meeting, a team of graphic designers at AXIA Innovation started working on the development of different versions of the logo. These versions were circulated for reviewing and approval inside the whole consortium. The objective was to capture the whole concept and mission of AGRICORE. After the comments were received and the partners cast their vote, the final version of the logo was agreed upon.

Figure 1 Voting procedure

Figure 2 Results Breakdown

2.1.2 Selected AGRICORE project Logo

The concept of the developed logo can be described as follows:

The logo was inspired by the interaction that will be developed between the decision-making AGRICORE tool and the farms. Essentially, the logo presents two linked pieces of a chain, agriculture and Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The combination of these leads to the AGRICORE tool that aims to mimic farmers’ behaviour along with their interactions to credibly evaluate the local effects of global events and EU policies, the improvement of policy design, perform impact assessments and carry out monitoring activities. The tool will be based on the advances in big data, artificial intelligence algorithms, mathematical solvers and cloud computing services.

The font of the logo is easy-to-read, with no footers to signify the ease of use of the platform developed by stakeholders, researchers and modellers.

Figure 3 Agricore Logo

2.1.3 Colour Scheme

The colour palettes of the logo were intentionally chosen. The green colour (code: #8eaf32) refers to agriculture, farms, plants etc and the blue petrol colour (code: #688b8a) refers to the technology-derived platform.

Figure 4 Agricore Logo Colour Scheme

Moreover, a second transparent version of the official logo has been designed to be used in many of the dissemination materials developed.

Figure 5 The AGRICORE Logo-transparent

2.2 AGRICORE templates

All the dissemination materials produced within the project are designed in line with the visual identity. Logos, printed materials and templates are available for partners to access and download from the internal communication platform (<https://confluence.agricore-project.eu>).

The following typography has been selected to be used in all dissemination materials:

2.2.1 Typography:

A distinctive and powerful typography reinforces the projects visual identity, adds character to key messages and enables communication with target groups more effectively.

- Title - typeface:

30 WORDS -American Typewriter

10PT CMYK: 100/9/89/30

- Core content - typeface:

160 WORDS -American Typewriter

12PT CMYK: 81/65/56/52

- Description of photos:

30 WORDS -American Typewriter

10PT CMYK: 100/9/89/30

2.2.2 PowerPoint template

In order to ensure widespread project recognition at conferences, workshops, various dissemination events as well as for internal meetings, a PowerPoint template has been prepared. It is tied to the visual style of the logo and the background image and a variety of formats and layouts are provided in the Master Slides. It consists of eleven slide designs, including a cover slide, an outline slide, two slides describing the positioning of the content presented in the project, three slides that can be used as a cover slide for different sections of a presentation, a slide for the description of the objectives, two slides for images and a final slide.

All slides include the EU emblem while the acknowledgement of European funding is embedded in the first and last slide:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 816078”.

Figure 6 Power Point Presentation template

2.2.3 Word - Confluence Template

The partners of the AGRICORE project decided in the early beginning of the project that the execution of the project would benefit if an enhanced collaboration among partners would be enforced. As part of the several actions done in this direction, the consortium decided to use the Confluence software for sharing knowledge between partners and to prepare all required official documents (deliverables). Confluence is a collaboration software program developed and published by Australian software company Atlassian. Among other useful functionalities, the suite allows for online real-time collaboration on documents, which has been adopted in the project deliverable preparation process. In order to export the information from the Confluence portal (e.g. into PDF documents), the software includes some built-in functionality. Nonetheless, AGRICORE partners desired more control over the format of the produced document and, accordingly, decided to install an additional third party plugin (Scroll Office exporter). This plugin allows for extended control of the exported documents including advanced formatting templates.

According to this, the project partners collaborated in the construction of a Word exporting template which will allow producing better-looking documents within the project. The template includes not only the typical Word styling aspects but also advanced macros for managing the exported content. The following figure shows an example of the core pages generated by such a template.

Table 1 Word template

2.2.4 Agenda Template

For simplification and time-saving purposes, a template of the agenda has been developed to be used for the preparation of all internal meetings as well as external events organized by the AGRICORE consortium.

Figure 7 Agenda template

2.2.5 Dissemination Template

A dissemination template has been prepared for the partners in order to present their participation in various events related to AGRICORE, disseminating the results and progress of the project in an easy and attractive way.

Figure 8 Dissemination template

2.2.6 AGRICORE email signature

An “AGRICORE related” email signature has been designed for each partner of the consortium to use in day-to-day communications. This could further enhance the communication activities of the project as well as help increase the social media presence of the project.

Figure 9 AGRICORE email signature

2.2.7 Printed Material

The visual identity has been developed starting from the project logo and applied to produce templates and printed materials which include the flyer/brochure, the roll-up, the folder, the lanyard, the newsletter and the press release. The idea behind this is to present the AGRICORE project in a professional and catchy way in the various dissemination events that partners will attend during the lifetime of the project. This will maximize the impact of the project by depicting the concept and the aim in a simple and memorable way.

Each item depicts the official logo and a brief description of the aim of the project. Moreover, they include all the logos of the partners as well as the QR code of the project. The EU emblem and the phrase “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 816078” are depicted as well.

2.2.7.1 Leaflet - Brochure

In order to provide the broad public, as early as possible, with information about the project, a general information leaflet about AGRICORE has been designed and approved by the consortium. The leaflet includes general project information such as the scope, the challenge and the impact expected from the project as well as the project partners, introducing the project concept in a simple and easy to read way.

The leaflet is additionally available on the AGRICORE website under “Outputs: Dissemination material” section and will be distributed to the public on request. It is a single sheet, letter size, tri-fold brochure, in English, with a clean, modern and attractive design which was created for dissemination purposes. The external side of the brochure presents the project logo & name and contains several information about the project (website, consortium members, project duration), the programme under which it has been funded and the logos of both the European Commission and the H2020. Additionally, the project’s domain name is given on the external page (see Figure 10). The internal part of the brochure is also structured in three pages. A brief description of the project’s main idea is presented on one page, along with the project challenges and the impact. In the internal part, a graphic representation of objectives is also given. The brochure is developed in order to be distributed for communication/dissemination and awareness-raising purposes to academics and stakeholders with an interest in AGRICORE during local events, conferences, or workshops. A printable version of the brochure is also available for use by partners.

Table 2 AGRICORE Leaflet

2.2.7.2 Roll-up

A first version of the roll-up has been designed with the highlights of the project in order to spread the word about it in the events organised by the consortium and to give visibility to the project at conferences and any event the consortium or any of its representatives participates in.

Figure 10 AGRICORE Roll-up

2.2.7.3 Folder

A presentation folder with a pocket that can hold relevant documents and papers has been created in line with the AGRICORE project visual identity. Not only does it have a functional usage but also helps to raise awareness about the Project providing memorable information about AGRICORE.

Figure 11 AGRICORE- Folder

2.2.7.4 Lanyard

A template of lanyards has been designed for use in Project meetings. They are useful and practical items, containing information about the partners (name, logo) and the meeting (date, place).

Figure 12 AGRICORE Lanyard

2.2.7.5 Press Release

The aim of the press releases is to attract media attention and increase public awareness of the AGRICORE project and its outcomes and events. The first project press release was published in September 2019 in order to inform about the kick-off of the project and its objectives (see Figure 14 below). Publications in magazines, press campaigns and media events will be supported by the preparation of additional press releases. All press releases will be available on the projects website and social media.

Figure 13 AGRICORE Press Release

2.2.7.6 Newsletters

During the project lifetime at least 6 electronic newsletters, providing information on the ongoing activities and results obtained, will be distributed not only amongst the AGRICORE partners' networks of contacts but also amongst further networks and platforms associated to mathematical and agent-based modelling, policy-making and policy impact assessment, as well as the social networks addressed.

2.2.8 Project website

Both the AGRICORE project and the AGRIMODELS cluster webpages have been developed and are part of the Corporate Identity of the project. Nonetheless, both webpages are described in a separate deliverable, specifically in D9.5 Project Website.

2.2.9 Social Media Profiles

Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn are currently the most popular social media with billions of users around the world. Social media have become the preference for many people who use them more than other traditional media, as they are inexpensive and easily accessible. Currently, Facebook claims to have over 2 billion active users, Twitter about 330 million users and LinkedIn nearly 500 million members. To benefit from these effective and freely available social media, AGRICORE has created profiles on all three media and has started sharing information about the project. The project profiles will serve as a complementary dissemination and communication channel in addition to the project website. They will include general project information with the aim to proactively promote the project and its results, permitting a two-way exchange. AGRICORE’s presence in social networks aims to accomplish the following specific objectives: a. Generate awareness and multiply the benefits from the communication efforts of all Consortium partners; b. Raise interest on the project topic in non-expert audiences; c. Promote the understanding of the knowledge, activities, and outcomes generated throughout the project; d. Promote feedback gathering, consultation and engaging with target groups; e. Enhance the project positioning in search engines results. Project partners are encouraged to visit these links and disseminate them within their professional and private networks. Access to social media is also supported on the project webpage. An evaluation of the accessibility and efficiency of these social media platforms in disseminating the relevant information and engaging the public will be made based on performance metrics, such as the number of visits, followers, comments, etc. The links to the project’s Social Media profiles appear below.

The Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/AGRICOREPROJECT/>) will be used for public project communication in the form of pictures and videos from meetings and outreach activities. This social media channel is set up to spread information to the general public.

Figure 14 AGRICORE Facebook page

The AGRICORE LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/28933736>) has been established as a community and facilitator for partners and stakeholders’ discussion and idea exchanges.

Figure 15 AGRICORE LinkedIn page

A strong Twitter presence (<https://twitter.com/AgricoreP>) spread across all of the target groups is important; therefore, the tweets cover all the project’s activities (i.e., events, training, conferences, calls), as well as a range of relevant topics such as news regarding modelling and ICT, big data, artificial intelligence algorithms and cloud computing services.

Figure 16 AGRICORE Twitter page

3 Conclusions

This deliverable contains all the information related to the development of AGRICORE project’s visual identity, as well as an overview of the project’s social media accounts screenshots. Communication and dissemination materials are also included. The visual identity of the AGRICORE project is a vital tool to create awareness among target audiences and support a broad range of activities and objectives throughout the project implementation.

At M4, the project activities related to communication and dissemination are in line with the activities foreseen under WP9–Communication and Dissemination both in terms of deliverables’ quality and timeline.

For preparing this report, the following deliverables have been taken into consideration:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due date
D9.4	AGRICORE corporate identity	AXIA Innovation	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	4